

Multimodal Quantification Of Postural Tremor

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Abstract. The recent decade has seen deadly viruses like HMPV, SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19), Ebola Virus etc which can be diagnosed and cured. Also, various preventive medicines and vaccines are invented for preventing the virus from affecting the individuals. There are other diseases which are predominantly getting increased in geriatric population in the recent years like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, Dementia, Sleep Disorder. These can be categorized as neurodegenerative diseases. The major challenge in these is that the neurologists are not able to diagnose this disease at an early stage and the progression of disease is quite rapid. When these diseases are detected and diagnosed at an early stage, there is a strong possibility to reduce the death rate and increase the patient's life span. This paper focuses on analysing the various methodologies and techniques currently available for diagnosing and detecting the major symptoms in Parkinson's patients termed as Tremor. The tremor can be either Rest tremor or Postural tremor. This is an early symptom of any Parkinson's patient. When this symptom is detected in an early stage, it can be a great relief to the care takers and also help the patient to lead a smooth life. A compressive survey of the methodologies, challenges and future enhancements are highlighted in this paper. The final results obtained is also analysed using parameters like Precision, Recall and Accuracy.

Keywords: Neurodegenerative · Parkinson's disease (PD) · Diagnosis

1 Introduction

Now a days, PD is becoming one of the major issues suffered by many people. PD is a movement disorder that occurs in various age groups of people. In the early days PD was dependent on certain factors like age but now it is becoming common in adults too. It is observed that PD occurs to men more than women. PD gets worse with time, so its early detection is very important. As we don't have any proper medication for this disease, early detection helps a lot in reducing the effects of PD quickly and effectively. Although the exact cause of PD [15] is still unknown, it is commonly believed that the condition primarily occurs due to damage, weakening, or death of neurons in brain (certain condition occur because of the loss of nerve cells in a part of the brain called the substantia nigra, these cells are responsible for making dopamine, when these cells are

Fig. 1. Common Symptoms in Parkinson's Disease Patients

lost, it can lead to various symptoms of PD). Most of the cases are sporadic. In PD, the nerve endings that produce a neurotransmitter norepinephrine [2] are lost, a key neurotransmitter controlling automatic functions such as heart rate and blood pressure. People observe issues with mobility, shaking, rigidity in the limbs or torso, or disrupted balance. As it gets worse with time people have problems in doing daily tasks like walking, talking and many more. However, the primary problem in diagnosing PD is that not everyone exhibiting one or more of these symptoms has PD, as several disorders can exhibit comparable symptoms as illustrated in the Figure 1. The four main symptoms of PD are tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability. Rate of progression of PD and symptoms varies in each person. This disease typically starts on one side of the body and eventually it affects both sides of the body. In people with PD development of Parkinson's gait tendency to lean forward, festination and reduced arm swing can be seen. They could have difficulty moving around and could stop unexpectedly while waking. Other problems accompanying PD are emotional changes, depression, difficulty swallowing and chewing, speech changes, urinary problems, skin problems, sleep problems, dementia, or other cognitive problems and many more. Currently, there aren't specific tests that can confirm PD. Doctors usually depend on subjects medical history and a check-up by a neurologist, blood and lab tests to rule out other possible causes of subjects symptoms, brain scans like CT or MRI, in rare situations where PD runs in the family, genetic testing can help determine the risk of developing the disease, surgery was also an option for PD before the discovery of levodopa. The cost of detecting PD is very high, and the process also takes a lot of time to detect the exact severity of PD. This motivates us to focus on the various methodologies and techniques which can be used for early detection using Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques. The major focus of this research work is to do an extensive analysis of current methodologies available to detect the postural tremor in PD and validate their results. The major contributions are tabulated in the Table 1. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses

about the related works, section 3 about the survey strategy followed, section 4 the methodologies, section 5 results and finally concluded with challenges and future scope.

Table 1. Contributions of Proposed Survey compared with Related Works

Ref.	Genetics	Treatment & Therapy	Economic Impact	Environment	Gender Difference	Comprehensive Study
[13]	×	✓	×	✓	×	✓
[14]	×	×	✓	×	×	✓
[17]	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
[6]	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓
[8]	×	×	×	✓	×	✓
[4]	×	×	×	✓	×	✓
[25]	×	×	×	×	✓	✓
[5]	✓	×	×	×	×	✓
Our Survey	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

2 Related Works

The study in [13] focuses on the effect of some respiratory disease like COVID-19 on PD subjects. This study addresses certain questions related to effect of COVID-19 on PD subject, its effect on PD subjects and associated outcomes. By doing a large amount of search span they found out that there is an impact on PD patients due to direct and indirect effects of SARS-CoV-2(COVID -2). Further findings are needed to know the effect of COVID-19 on PD. Subjects with PD experience both motor and non-motor complications. The authors in [14] mainly focus on the expenditure faced by the patient. The overall cost may vary from country to country. An inpatient care and nursing home cost takes the larger component while the prescribed medicines act as the smallest contributor. The authors, in [17], found that music therapy can significantly benefit PD patients across various domains. Music therapy shows notable improvements in motor functions, social communication, emotional well-being, and cognitive abilities in PD patients. They found out that music-based interventions such as rhythmic auditory stimulation (RAS) enhance gait stability, stride length, and motor coordination and has overall effects in reducing the effects of PD. The author in [6] mainly focused on the in-depth meaning of PD along with its cause, care and treatment needed for it. The author emphasized the rising global concern of PD, which can be caused due to genetic and non-genetic factors. They discuss the cause of Diagnostic criteria, and the need for personalized management strategies. The paper highlights that there are no treatments to slow or stop Parkinson’s progression yet, but ongoing research is working to find new options.

It provides a clear overview of PD and emphasizes the importance of personalized care and future treatment advancements. The author in [8] talk about the “PD prevention agenda”. The global incidence of PD is rising worldwide. Several diseases have several environmental and genetic influences no therapy which is approved for the disease. As there are various environmental pesticides, metals are implicated in PD , and prevention of disease is possible. They have identified preclinical and clinical research goals that emphasize primary prevention and disease prediction in an effort to reduce the burden of PD. PD is a complex brain disorder that affects around 10 million people worldwide. It comes in two forms: familial and sporadic, with its causes likely involving a mix of genetic and environmental factors. Unfortunately, by the time these symptoms appear, significant brain damage has already occurred. There’s no cure yet, and current treatments focus on managing symptoms. Diagnoses are made through observing symptoms and how well a person responds to dopamine-based treatments. The number of people with PD varies across the world, influenced by factors like age, gender, genetics, and the environment. This study [4] explores how environmental factors may contribute to PD, aiming to better understand its causes and open innovations for new treatments. In [25] the author studies why PD is more common in males than females, but the reasons for this difference remains unclear. This study aimed to update knowledge about gender differences in PD exists through a systematic review and meta-analysis. The overall male-to- female prevalence ratio (OPR) was found to be 1.18, meaning PD affects slightly more males. Factors like study design, national wealth, or participant age did not explain these differences. The study highlights the need for further research into other factors, such as genetics, environment, and healthcare access, to better understand gender-related differences in PD. The authors , in [5], found out that PD is a complex neurodegenerative disorder influenced by both rare and common genetic variants. Mutations in over 20 genes are linked to PD, with causing early onset. Genome wide association studies (GWAS) have identified 90 independent risk associated variants. PD risk variants are often located near known PD related genes and genes associated with lysosomal functions (digestion, immune response, programmed cell death, nutrient sensing). Significant progress has been made in understanding PD’s genetic basis, but much work remains. The related work focuses on PD research, exploring its effects, costs, and treatment. It discusses the impact of COVID-19 on PD subjects, the benefits of music therapy, genetic and environmental causes, gender differences, and advances in understanding PD through genetic studies, while highlighting the need for personalized care and prevention strategies. Though there are multiple comprehensive surveys available, there is no extensive survey concentrating on all the aspects related to postural tremor analysis. These signify particularly on the concept of PD, while our paper mainly focuses on various ML algorithms and methodologies used to detect an early stage of postural tremor in PD. We have drafted a comparative analysis in this paper based on different researches and techniques equipped by researchers across the world.

3 Literature Search Strategies

The search strategy followed and the screening process is illustrated in the Figure 2 PubMed searches were done during the month of June 2024 with the keywords “Parkinson’s”, “symptoms”, “tremor”, “clinical strategy”, “non-invasive treatments” and “invasive treatments”. We restricted the year of publications to be from 2022 onwards. From the publications, we screened based on the relevance. Then, we tried to identify relevant publications related to ML and “Parkinson’s Tremor Analysis” using the Scopus database. The articles published since 2022 were considered. We then grouped them based on various modalities used for assessing the tremor especially postural tremor. We landed with 57 articles and after removing duplicates, we scrutinized based on postural tremor and finally landed with 20 articles.

Fig. 2. Search and Screening Strategy

4 Methodologies

4.1 Change in regularity

The author in [23] conducted their experiment on 8 subjects and 8 PD patients. It’s very well-known that almost all PD patients exhibit bilateral disorder, they used questionnaire and Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) [10] for analyzing which limb was most affected. The results obtained using both methods were the same. Out of 8 subjects, 4 subjects showed disorder in the left limb and other 4 in the right limb. All the patients were right-handed. During the testing, the subjects and patients were asked to perform three tremor tasks each for 30 secs and three trials were postural hand tremor, postural finger tremor

and resting tremor. In order to measure the limb acceleration, they used surface electromyography (EMG) which acted as preamplifiers. The Extensor digitorum communis (EDC) muscle was responsible for controlling active extension, while the Flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS) muscle managed the hand and the finger flexion. The data management and optimization techniques of the acceleration and EMG were done using digital correction, down sampling, digital filtering and MATLAB software for the analysis of kinematic variability, power related to tremor and low frequencies. After recording the consistency of movement, the rectified signals were used to calculate the level of neuromuscular activity and with the use of Fourier analysis, finger acceleration and EMG activity in EDC and FDS muscles, with auto-spectral analysis and peak power determination within frequency bins were examined in detail. The two techniques which were used to investigate tremor dynamics were the proportion of power at each frequency and approximation entropy (ApEn) [19] in the time domain. The study used cross - ApEn to analyze the relationship between acceleration and EMG activity over time, focusing on how the connection between acceleration, EMG, and the activity of extensor and flexor muscles changed.

4.2 Electrophysiological assessment

The research conducted by the author in [9] included 73 subjects which were diagnosed with idiopathic PD based on the UK Brain Bank Criteria excluding the patients with neurologic comorbidity, signs of psychogenic tremor or substantial cognitive impairment. Estimating the subjects in both “On” and “Off” state, Movement Disorders Society UPDRS, H-Y Scale, and Fahn Tolosa-Marin Tremor Rating Scale were used in the clinical assessment [11]. To analyze the tremor characteristics, EMG measurements were performed. Patients were asked to rest on a pillow while lying and their hands hung freely. This was designed to see the amount of shaking (tremor) in their hands. The four situations that were tested are:

- a. REST : Hands of the subjects were hanging freely.
- b. POSH: Making the subject’s wrists and fingers horizontal
- c. POST: Subjects lifted both arms to shoulder height and held their wrists and fingers at a horizontal level.
- d. WEIGHT: in addition with POST, they were asked to lift a weight of 0.5kg. These stages lasted for one minute except the weight, which was done for one time. The experiment was repeated three times during rest, twice each for post and posh, and once for weight. The average was calculated, and EMG was used to measure tremors.

4.3 Wearable device to measure signals with Support Vector Machine (SVM)

In [1] authors had, a total of 14 subjects without PD emulate the effects of PD. Here to replicate the effect of postural tremor they had to hold their hands

in front of their body for 25 to 30 seconds. They tried to create different postural intensities to match the UPDRS scores. The subjects had to wear the Physilog Gold wireless inertial measurement unit around their wrist and one extended part to their index finger. This unit had various types of sensors like 3D accelerometer, 3D gyroscope, 3D magnetometer and one barometric pressure sensor. The sampling frequency was set to 200Hz. In the next step, the data collected from all 14 people was processed. The processing which they used was already done by some researchers before but the difference here was that some additional sensors signals were found, and Welch's method of spectrum analysis was used. By analysing, they got the tremor window between 3.5 and 7.5Hz. By the above process three sets of postural tremor trials were found which were then put into feature extraction algorithm. The natural logarithm of RMS of linear acceleration for an accelerometer or angular velocity for gyroscope was calculated. By comparing results, it was found that it was correlating. Again, the natural logarithm of peak power was taken into consideration, and it was also correlating with UPDRS clinical scores. Now for final classification extracted features were fed to SVM with linear kernel with 5-fold cross validation model. 5-Fold Cross Validation is a technique used to evaluate the performance of a ML model by dividing the dataset into 5 subsets. The model is trained and validated 5 times, each time using a different subset as the validation set and the remaining 4 subsets as the training set. The final performance metric is the average of the metrics from all 5 folds. For this classification process around 33 postural tremor trials were used.

4.4 Set of wearable sensors with Hidden Markov Model (HMM)

The author in [20] involved 23 subjects, divided into three groups (10 PD patients with tremor symptoms, 8 PD patients without tremor symptoms but with other symptoms, and 5 healthy individuals without any medical condition). The subjects were given tasks with UPDRS scores and transmitted through ZigBee protocol to a PC. For the quantification of postural tremor, they first attached some sensors to body parts [16] of subjects (body parts were right wrist, left wrist, right leg, left leg, waist, chest). The whole process is based on data recovered from accelerometers attached to subjects. From this data many features were created based on many different factors like related time and frequency-domain characteristics. To distinguish between tremor types some spatial features were also extracted. So, to start the process subjects were told to be in particular positions and postures. To calculate the postural tremor subjects were told to keep their hands extended while they were standing. The data before feeding to HMM[24] model, it was first passed through loss-pass finite-impulse-response (FIR) filter which gives the Low Frequency (LF) component which corresponds to PD patients' movement due to other PD motor symptoms. Besides this it was passed through bandpass FIR filter to extract the High Frequency (HF) component which corresponds to movements caused by tremors. From these filtered signals two sets of features were extracted, one for body position recognition and one for tremor detection and quantification. After extracting these features, it

was fed to HMM but before that the HMM was trained against some specific parameters (Prior Probability of the states, State transition matrix, parameters of output distribution of each state). The trained model then used the extracted features[7] and gave two types of results. One, it categorized the body positions in five states. Second, the tremor severity was categorized into 5 states (S-0 to S-3 plus other states). S-0 as no tremor to S-3 as moderate tremor. The classifier used was Naive Bayes classifier. Then they removed bias. To classify the position and tremor severity of the patient, a leave-one- patient-out cross- validation technique was used.

4.5 Tremor changes during voluntary movement and limb loading tasks

The author [12] of this research paper conducted a test for 7 subjects out of which 4 were males and 3 females aged around 69.3 ± 8.4 years. Experienced neurologist's, highly professionalized in diagnosis of postural tremor was consulted and he identified four patients with PD and three with essential postural tremor. The participants performed two-armed movement tasks consecutively: the first task was without any load whereas the second involved placing 0.5kg weight on each wrist. Each task was timed for 6 minutes and 20 seconds. The task consists of 21 segments positioned their arms as instructed by the instructor. The MATLAB based tool was used and it has a representation denoting two balls, one blue and one red, representing the arms. Sometimes the balls are on the right screen and other times on the left. At the start the balls are at the bottom of the screen denoting the resting position of participant's hand. Then the balls slowly move up, as if you are lifting your arm. They stop when they reach the top of the screen like your arms fully raised up to shoulder level. This whole process took 10 sec in total, 5 sec up and 5 sec down. This process happens 6 times for each arm, one with nothing in the hands(unloaded) and once with some weight in hands(loaded).

4.6 Classification with two-stage deep neural network

In this research paper the author's [18] conducted Timed Up and Go test with 87 subjects. This task was basically created to evaluate balance, coordination and mobility in PD patients. The task was divided into 4 subtasks: going directly to a chair, turning around, and walking back to the starting point after 30 seconds of balance maintenance. This study aims to assess the efficiency of a combined input for detecting early stages of PD through a functional assessment test using sensors. The model has 2 stages and uses biomechanical data, raw sensor data, and frequency analysis as inputs. The study also compares this model with simpler models that use only one type of input, such as raw signals, frequency analysis, or biomechanical variables alone. Additionally, it evaluates the accuracy of a Convolutional Neural Networks(CNN) [21] in automatically segmenting the signals and calculating biomechanical variables from raw data. An inertial sensor was embedded in smartphone was used. The sensor was attached to the lower

back using a strap. The test utilized the FallSkip [22] system app, a commercial product by IBV (Instituto de Biomecánica de Valencia, a Spanish research institute), to conduct the test, record signals, and manage testing times. All data processing and analysis were done offline ensuring the independence and accuracy of the analysis from the recording system. The first stage includes three steps: signal preprocessing, functional test segmentation, and signal feature extraction. The second stage involves windowing and model inputs, which include time-domain analysis, frequency domain analysis, and biomechanical variables.

Table 2. Results for Different Methods Used in the Study

Ref. No	Dataset	Result
[23][10][19]	8 subjects and 8 normal people	Decrease in ApEn for Parkinson’s patients. EMG Signal Analysis: Reduction in 20–25 Hz tremor component. Increase in 8–12 Hz tremor region.
[9][11]	73 subjects	Revealed 2 phenotypes: re-emergent tremor (81%), pure postural tremor (19%).
[1]	14 subjects	(a) 78.8% (b) 81.8%
[20][16][7][24]	23 subjects	Max accuracy of tremor severity classification 87%.
[12]	7 subjects	Significant differences in tremors between baseline and top position.
[18][21][22]	87 subjects	CNN + Long Short Term Memory(LSTM): 86.42%, CNN + biomechanical: 92.23%, Two-stage model: 99.64%.

5 Results And Discussion

This paper mainly focuses on the different methods used by scientists to detect PD and their comparison with other similar research, we discuss the best way and the most effective way with highest accuracy and minimum limitations which is time and cost effective as depicted in Table 2. Neurologists have traditionally been involved in the diagnosis of PD. However, the evaluation they conducted was riddled with errors: they were unable to determine the severity of PD in a single study; they were unable to monitor the patient round-the-clock; they could not do live monitoring; and their detection process was cumbersome and lengthy, which allowed PD to worsen and become severe. To solve these problems scientists and researchers are making new discoveries to achieve the highest accuracy possible and to detect the problem quickly. There has been research on this topic for many years now and so many different algorithms have been developed in these years. In the study [23], the author considered 8 normal people and 8 PD patients. As we know PD affects both the left and right part of the

body and using questionnaire and UPDRS and motor-section we can infer that it affects limbs the most. The research used a method called cross-ApEn to look at how the patterns of movement (acceleration) and muscle activity (EMG) relate to each other over time. They wanted to see how the connection between these two things changed, especially for the muscles involved in extending and flexing. After the experiment a key factor in tremor was observed which is the significant decrease in ApEn for the PD patients. Researchers have noticed a 10% decrease in symptoms among people with PD. The study also used ApEn to see how the activity of muscles that straighten(extensor), and bend(flexor) are related in people with PD. However, the study is not applicable for advanced stages of the disease. There is another study using electrophysiologic assessment which was conducted [9] for a set of 73 patients. The study was conducted to analyze muscle activity and shaking in the hands. The experiment revealed two different tremor phenotypes Re-emergent which is 81% and Post Postural Tremor which is 19%. Although the model was accurate, it was not fully generalized for PD patients. The classification was dependent on various factors and patients' response to medication varied. Also, this research did not explore long-term implications or the progression of these tremor types. Right now, there is one more way which is getting popular and showing so much potential to give the max accuracy possible. The way we are talking about is ML and AI. ML is making research so quick and efficient. Some authors [1], used a wearable device with various sensors to get the data they needed to predict PD. They took the data from the sensor and fed it to SVM. This made processing data and predicting the output so much faster. Yet it was not perfected to its full capacity to give us 100% accuracy. Their model only gave around 81.8% accuracy at max. ML offers accurate results but requires proper dataset and algorithm. Manual methods take time, effort and increasing error. ML solves these issues, providing quick results for fast treatment and early tremor recognition. To achieve the highest accuracy possible, another group of researchers [15] used different ML algorithm. They also used a similar way of taking the data from wearable sensors with a greater number of data sensors. The difference they had in their model was that they used HMM model and rather than directly recognizing the tremor severity, they found two types of results. Firstly, they found the position and action/posture the patients were in and secondly the tremor severity ranging from S-0 to S-3. The accuracy of their ML model was 87%. This shows that having different ML algorithms and different datasets also changes accuracy to a greater extent. The SVM ML model used by the authors [1] was not as effective as the model used by the author in the study [20]. So, choosing or creating a better model according to the needs is also important. While the other study [12] focuses on tremor pattern in PD and postural tremor patients during arm movement tasks(loaded and unloaded). Results showed similar movement frequencies between the two group, but significant tremor differences were observed in the unloaded conditions. Despite careful analysis, no noticeable effect of weights on tremors was found, consistent with previous research. Radar charts illustrated tremor changes over time, with significant differences noted between baseline and top arm positions. However,

the impact of weights on tremors was inconclusive. Further research with larger patient groups and similar tremor character may give different outcomes. The study says that there is the need for more targeted investigations to better understand these mechanisms and their implications for treatment. However, one more study [18] yielded the best outcome among those compared models where researchers utilized two- stage CNN to classify early stages of PD based on data from the Timed Up and Go test. The results demonstrated high accuracy, with the proposed model achieving 99.64%. This outperformed other models, including those high biochemical variables or CNN with LSTM. However, caution is warranted due to the small sample size and potential biases related to varying PD stages.

6 Challenges

Based on the researches compared in this paper, we do find an accuracy which can be utilized, but they also come with a few limitations. The findings may not fully generalize to all PD patients. The classification relied on a specific set of criteria, and individual responses to medication varied. Some techniques did not explore long-term implications or the progression of these tremor types. The sample size for pure postural tremor was relatively small(19%), which may impact the generalizability of findings and in some other techniques the combination of both finger and wrist also gives a promising result but furthermore investigations are needed. The study on tremor changes during voluntary movement and limb loading tasks has several limitations. The small sample size of only seven participants makes it challenging to draw reliable conclusions. Additionally, the participants were primarily older adults, limiting the diversity of the study group and potentially overlooking how tremors might behave in younger individuals. The research also failed to find significant effects of adding weights on tremor patterns, raising questions about whether the method used was sensitive enough to detect subtle differences. Furthermore, the grouping of patients with similar tremor characteristics wasn't explored in depth, which might have revealed more meaningful insights. These factors highlight the need for more extensive and diverse studies to better understand tremor behavior. Future research should address these limitations by incorporating a modified scale with intermediate stages and validating findings with larger, more diverse datasets. Also expanding validation to multiple centers and including complementary diagnostic tools can enhance the clinical relevance and reliability of the classification model.

7 Conclusion

This research work mainly focused on providing a comprehensive survey of the various techniques currently available for diagnosing the symptoms of PD patient. We also tried to summarize the various developments in early detection of

the tremor in PD like experiments related to change in regularity and Electrophysiological assessments. Also, the usage of wearable devices for the same purpose is extensively discussed. Apart from this, certain researchers have also focused on developing AI based techniques using ML and Deep Learning [3]. Due to the advancement in all the latest techniques, there is a hope that the symptoms can be detected at an early stage of PD hence increasing the lifetime of the patients there by providing a relief to the care takers.

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